

AWARENESS TOWARDS NEP-2020 AMONG SECONDARY TEACHER EDUCATORS

Vijay Singh

Research Scholar, Department of Education, Himachal Pradesh University Shimla

E-mail id: vijusinghviijay@gmail.com

Ajay Kumar Attri

Professor, Department of Education, Himachal Pradesh University Shimla

E-mail id: ajayattrihpu@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 20 MAR 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 APRIL 2025

Published On: 01 MAY 2025

Abstract

This study examines the awareness and knowledge of National Education Policy (NEP-2020) among secondary teacher educators in Himachal Pradesh, having special emphasis on various demographic variables. India's major educational reform of 21st i.e. NEP-2020 aims to enhance quality, inclusivity and interdisciplinary learning, thereby transforming the whole educational landscape of the country. It is very crucial to understand the role of the secondary teacher educators along with their awareness of the policy to effectively implement it at grassroot level. This study by using structured survey and statistical analysis tried to identify key trends and demographic differences in the levels of awareness. Findings and conclusions indicate that awareness differs significantly based on certain factors under consideration, highlighting the need for targeted training and professional development. The results of the research offer insights for policymakers and education administrators to improve the understanding and implementation of NEP-2020 across educational institutions.

Keywords: NEP-2020, Awareness, Teacher Educators, Implementation.

INTRODUCTION

It is said that a country's educational system shapes its goals, outlook, and identity. Given the changes in technology, knowledge systems, and globalization, institutions must adapt to ensure learners are equipped with the necessary competencies and appreciable values in the 21st century. In the context of this particular framework, India introduced the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, which aims to transform the entire structure of education from

foundational learning through secondary schooling, post-secondary education core, lifelong learning, and skill development. In order to meet the demands of the twenty-first century, the policy places a strong emphasis on flexible, trans-disciplinary, learner-centered, and holistic education. NEP 2020 aims to bring about significant changes in the governance, curriculum, and structure of education. It promotes basic literacy and numeracy, inclusive and equitable education, vocational education integration, teacher empowerment, and the advancement of Indian languages and culture. Its emphasis on teacher education and capacity building, which acknowledges teachers as the central figure in the learning process, is especially noteworthy. All teacher education programs are expected to be housed in interdisciplinary institutions by 2030, with a focus on producing top-notch teachers via the four-year integrated B.Ed. degree and ongoing professional development.

The awareness, understanding, and preparedness of teacher educators particularly those at the secondary level, become increasingly important in realizing the policy objectives associated with these ambitious reforms. Teacher educators are the fundamental supporting and working within the lines of preparation of teachers, responsible for rendering policy into practice, and developing teachers skills, attitudes, and knowledge appropriate within the education context and pedagogical framework provided. Without adequate understanding of NEP 2020, these teachers may not be able to contextualize their instruction and activities to the desired outcomes of the policy. While NEP 2020 has been the subject of much discussion by academics and policymakers, there is limited empirical evidence to assess the awareness and understanding of secondary level teachers educators.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, after a period of more than thirty years, is a huge metamorphosis for the Indian educational system. The education of educators, especially those involved in teacher education, is pivotal here as it relates to the awareness and readiness of the system and its stakeholders. There are many studies that have looked at how well-informed different stakeholders (e.g., bureaucrats, educators) are about NEP 2020, signalling important information about the current state of policy awareness. Several studies have been able to look specifically at levels of awareness and attitudes toward NEP 2020 in relation to school teachers, college faculty, and educational administrators.

Kumar and Sharma (2021) conducted a study on levels of understanding NEP 2020 by school teachers in Haryana, which also revealed lower awareness levels and were obtained in conjunction with mostly webinars and social media. Singh and Mishra (2022) also reported

that while most college teachers totally supported the reforms proposed by NEP 2020, there existed tremendous confusion relating the momentum, mechanisms and timelines. Rani (2021) in her survey of teacher trainees, identified other gaps in terms of conceptual clarity at the level of understanding at the level of NEP components such as the 5+3+3+4 structure, multi-disciplinary learning and the NCFTE changes.

Teacher educators play a vital role in interpreting policy provisions and embedding them in pre-service teacher training. Bhattacharya (2020) highlighted the critical role of teacher educators as an intermediary between policy and practice. However, the study found an absence of institutional readiness for aligning the teacher education curriculum to the NEP 2020 guidelines. Naik and Pillai (2021) surveyed B.Ed. college faculty in Maharashtra and found that only 40% had attended professional development sessions on NEP 2020, underscoring the need for targeted capacity-building programs.

Further, Saxena and Verma (2022) explored awareness levels among educators across urban and rural regions and found significant differences, with urban educators generally more informed due to better access to resources and professional networks. Ali and Jahan (2021) considered gender differences in the awareness of NEP 2020. They found no statistical evidence of differences in awareness, leading to the conclusion that the policy outreach efforts appeared to be uniform, irrespective of gender. Sharma and Kaul (2021), analysed how digital platforms helped to raise NEP awareness during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The study found that online seminars and government portals like Diksha and SWAYAM served as major sources of information for educators. Chatterjee (2022) emphasized the role of institutional leadership and state-level workshops in enhancing NEP awareness among higher education faculty.

Although these studies offer fundamental insights into the broader knowledge of NEP 2020, little study has focused on secondary teacher educators, a group that is crucial in forming the next generation of educators. Furthermore, little research has been done on the ways in which factors like location, gender, and educational background affect awareness levels. The sources of information and their relationship to awareness level have not been thoroughly studied in many studies. The literature analysis emphasizes the need for targeted studies on secondary teacher educators' knowledge of NEP 2020. Knowing the level of their policy awareness is crucial since they play a part in forming teacher competencies that are in line with national objectives. By offering empirical data and insights that help guide NEP

2020 training, distribution, and implementation methods within the teacher education ecosystem, this study seeks to close this significant gap.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Teachers are arguably the most important members of our society. They give children purpose, set them for success as citizen of our world and inspire in them a derive to do well and succeed in life. The children of today are leaders of tomorrow, teachers are that point that makes child ready for their future. So, it becomes must for teachers to be more knowledgeable and aware of what's going around and also about researches and advancements going on in field of education. They act as a channel between policy and classroom learning. Their awareness of NEP-2020 ensures that the principles and reforms of the policy are effectively communicated to pre-service teachers and ultimately translated into real. Different demographic groups (e.g., gender, locality, stream of education) may have varying levels of access to or engagement with policy updates. Understanding these variations can help tailor professional development initiatives to the unique needs of diverse educator groups. Few studies directly address secondary teacher educators, a crucial group for the implementation and dissemination of policy, despite the fact that several have assessed NEP-2020 understanding among faculty members in higher education or among school instructors.

The findings of this study provide evidence-informed perspectives on areas of awareness gaps that could inform policymakers, curriculum writers, and educational leaders in designing targeted interventions and professional development initiatives. It could help to establish consistent understanding if we determine whether all secondary teacher educators, regardless of gender, location, educational institution or information source, hold a similar understanding of NEP-2020 reforms. By examining awareness levels and how they are affected, the study could further improve the quality of teacher education programs, making them more relevant for the aims of NEP-2020 such as competency-based education, inclusive education, and transdisciplinary approaches to education. The study could also inform future studies that investigate the challenges that future educators will face in implementing NEP-2020 and where teacher educators fit in to drive educational change.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the awareness of NEP-2020 among male and female secondary teacher educators.

2. To study the awareness of NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators based on their locale.
3. To study the awareness of NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators with regard to their academic stream.
4. To study the awareness of NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators based on their sources of information.

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be no significant difference in awareness of NEP-2020 between male and female secondary teacher educators.
2. There will be no significant difference in awareness of NEP-2020 between rural and urban secondary teacher educators.
3. There will be no significant difference in awareness of NEP-2020 between arts and science stream educators.
4. There will be no significant difference in awareness based on the sources of information about NEP-2020.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey method was adopted. A 42-item questionnaire developed via Google Forms was used to assess awareness levels across educational topics from ECCE to higher education. Data were collected through email and WhatsApp.

SAMPLE

In the present study the target population was Secondary Teacher Educators i.e. Assistant Professors of private B.Ed. colleges affiliated to Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla. A total of 98 secondary teacher educators (Assistant Professors) were selected randomly for the present study.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In the present study, 't-test' was used to analyze the data. The level of significance of t-values was checked at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. To achieve the objectives of the present study, the obtained data from secondary teacher educators were organized in a form suited to testing the hypotheses. The descriptions of calculations and results obtained have been systematically presented as:

Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Secondary Teacher Educators as related to Gender: To compare the significant difference in mean scores of awareness towards NEP-2020 among male and female secondary teacher educators, their means, standard deviations,

and 't'-value were calculated. The means, standard deviations, and 't'-value are given in Table 1.

Table 1
Difference in Mean Scores of Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Male and Female Secondary Teacher Educators

Sr. No.	Gender	Mean	S.D.	N	t-value	df	Sig.
1.	Male	29.36	7.44	22	0.27	96	NS
2.	Female	29.75	5.64	76			

NS=Not Significant

From the above table it may be observed that t-value of .27 was found to be non-significant at .05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference in awareness towards NEP-2020 among male and female secondary teacher educators.

Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Secondary Teacher Educators as related to Locality: To compare the significant difference between mean scores of awareness towards NEP-2020 among rural and urban secondary teacher educators, their means, standard deviations, and 't'-value were calculated. The means, standard deviations, and 't'-value are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Sr. No.	Locality	Mean	S.D.	N	t-value	df	Sig.
1.	Rural	31.08	4.34	59	2.98	96	S
2.	Urban	27.51	7.53	39			

S=Significant

This table indicates that the t-value comparing significant difference in mean scores of awareness towards NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators having rural and urban background came out to be 2.98 and came out to be significant at .01 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in awareness towards NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators having rural and urban background. Further secondary teacher educators having rural background had more awareness towards NEP-2020 as compare to their counterpart secondary teacher educators having urban background.

Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Secondary Teacher Educators as related to their Streams of study: To compare the significant difference between mean scores of awareness

towards NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators having arts and science streams, their means, standard deviations, and 't'-value were calculated. The means, standard deviations, and 't'-value are given in Table 3.

Table 3
Difference in Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Secondary Teacher Educators having Arts and Science Streams

Sr. No.	Stream	Mean	S.D.	N	't' value	df	Sig.
1.	Arts	29.60	6.05	57	0.51	96	NS
2.	Science	30.22	5.79	41			

This table reveals that t-value .51 was not significant even at 0.5 level of significance; it means that secondary teacher educators having arts and science streams had almost similar awareness towards NEP-2020. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Secondary Teacher Educators as related to their source of information for NEP-2020

To assess the significant difference in mean scores of awareness towards NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators as related to their source of information for NEP-2020, the means, standard deviations, and 't'-value were calculated. The means, standard deviations, and 't'-value are presented in Table 4.

1

Table 4
Difference in Awareness towards NEP-2020 among Secondary Teacher Educators as related to their source of information for NEP-2020

Sr. No.	Sources of Information	Mean	S.D.	N	't' values	df	Sig.
1.	Mass Media	29.44	6.26	55	0.42	96	NS
2.	Online FDPs*	29.95	5.82	43			

FDPs =Faculty Development Programs

Table exhibits that t-value of 0.42 reflecting no significant difference in mean scores of awareness towards NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators who used mass media or attended online FDPs as a source of information for NEP-2020. It may be concluded that secondary teacher educators who used mass media or attended online FDPs as a source of information for NEP-2020 had almost similar awareness towards NEP-2020. Hence the null hypothesis was retained.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

When it comes to awareness of NEP-2020 there's no notable difference between male and female secondary teacher educators, both groups show similar level of understanding, so we can say that gender is not a deciding factor of difference about engagement to education policy.

However there is a significant gap in awareness between secondary teacher educators from rural and urban backgrounds. Those from rural areas tend to be more informed about NEP-2020 compared to their urban counterparts. However this finding is somewhat contradictory as par with usual findings of others but this may be due to many governing factors.

Interestingly there's no significant difference in awareness of NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators who studied in arts versus those in sciences; both groups exhibits similar levels of awareness. Lastly the source of information doesn't seem to impact awareness levels regarding NEP-2020 among secondary teacher educators. Whether they rely on mass media or online faculty development programs, their level of understanding towards NEP-2020 remains on par.

CONCLUSION

This study sheds light on how aware secondary teacher educators are of NEP-2020, offering several valuable insights that could shape and help future educational plans and strategies. As very first finding shown that gender doesn't play a significant role in awareness levels both male and female educators showed similar grasp of the policy, this finding is in line with previous research that found no major gender differences. On other hand the lower awareness among urban educators suggests a need to reassess urban policy dissemination strategies. Despite of better facilities, infrastructure there may be gaps in engagement or perception of relevance among urban secondary teacher educators. Personalised or tailored programs and workshops in urban areas may help in engagement or perception and understanding among secondary teacher educators. The uniformity of awareness across arts and sciences disciplines supports the idea of unified professional development modules ensuring equal alignment in understanding and implementation of policy. Finally the use of various sources also shown equal effectiveness which means institutions should continue to use a blend of both formal and informal sources i.e. FDPs and media, social platforms for disseminating information.

REFERENCES

- Ali, S., & Jahan, R. (2021). A study of awareness towards National Education Policy 2020 among school teachers in Delhi. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 10(4), 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.35629/2456-0006>
- Bhattacharya, A. (2020). NEP 2020 and teacher educators: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Educational Policy and Administration*, 4(2), 30–35.
- Chatterjee, S. (2022). Institutional leadership and faculty awareness of NEP 2020 in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 36(1), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-06-2022-0263>
- Kumar, R., & Sharma, M. (2021). An assessment of NEP 2020 awareness among school teachers in Haryana. *Journal of Teacher Education and Research*, 16(1), 101–108.
- Naik, S., & Pillai, R. (2021). Awareness and preparedness for NEP 2020 among teacher educators in Maharashtra. *International Journal of Research in Education and Psychology*, 5(2), 42–49.
- Rani, P. (2021). Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among pre-service teacher trainees. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 12(3), 70–78.
- Saxena, A., & Verma, K. (2022). Urban-rural disparities in NEP 2020 awareness among educators: A comparative study. *Journal of Rural and Urban Education Studies*, 8(1), 15–23.
- Sharma, V., & Kaul, M. (2021). The role of ICT in disseminating NEP 2020: Perspectives from educators during the pandemic. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26, 7453–7467. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10644-5>
- Singh, P., & Mishra, A. (2022). Perception and understanding of NEP 2020 among higher education faculty in Uttar Pradesh. *Journal of Indian Education*, 48(2), 44–53.